

Tribal Medicine Practices in Kadugolla Tribes : A Sociological Study of Chitradurga District

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ABSTRACT

Traditional medicine may include formalized aspects of folk medicine, that is to say longstanding remedies passed on and practiced by lay people. Folk medicine consists of the healing practices and ideas of body physiology and health preservation known to some in a culture, transmitted informally as indigenous knowledge, and practiced or applied by anyone in the culture having prior experience. In this study various medicinal practices has been observed and used by families of Chitradurga district. The tribal people like kadugolla's are used these plants to treat different diseases. The use of these herbal medicines has important role in the modern medicine system like Ayurveda, unani sidda, homeopathy, etc. The use of herbal medicine is not only cost effective but also safe and almost free from serious side effects. A total 35 medicinal plant species distributed in Chitradurga district. Nomadic-Semi nomadic tribal families are practicing this traditional medicinal system as an alternate occupation along with agriculture and animal rearing. These medicinal plants are used for headache, earache, stomach-ache, antioxidants, liver diseases, renal disease, anti- diabetic, wound infections, skin infections, fever, cough, diarrhea, eye infections, general weakness, blood purifier, to enhance immunity and other several diseases.

Keywords: Kadugolla, Nomadic Tribe, Semi nomadic Tribe, Herbal Medicine, Pashupalak

INTRODUCTION

Tribals are the original inhabitants of the world. There are many types in them. The tribal do 'pashupalak' (Rearing of animals) occupation, since their ancestors

lived in the forest land. They have strong ancestral bond with the forests; they existed by rearing of animals. Today they are called Semi nomadic groups of tribal. Chitradurga is a range of south India. The range rises in regional backward areas in Karnataka state. In this district majority of the peoples are adapted to agricultural activities.

According to recent study of United Nations of organization up to 20% of the world population tribal people, they identified and leading life with their own ancestral cultural activities and ancestral pursuits. Tribal lived in forest along with rearing of animals and agriculture they also involve in preparation of baskets, furniture's, medicines using forest products. The future tribal generations also follow and continues their ancestor pursuit. Especially tribes still continued traditional medicine system of nomadic and semi nomadic community named as 'Kadugolla'. The present study concentrates how Kadugolla community continued these cultural practices.

India is well known for its plant diversity and is rich in medicinal plants wealth. India has the second largest tribal population in the world after Africa. According to the 1991 census of India, the total tribal population is 6% of country's population of which Karnataka has 51 scheduled tribe communities along with the total population of the state. The traditional medicinal practices are an important part of primary healthcare systems in the developing countries (Ghosh, 2003). As per World Health Organization (1978) report as much as 80% population of the world depends on traditional herbal medicine for

their primary healthcare necessities (Azaizeh et al., 2003). The tribal people don't have much knowledge of the education but they have the knowledge of traditional medicines and their uses as the remedies to various diseases. This knowledge is transmitted from one generation to the next generation.

METHODOLOGY:

Research topic: -

Tribal Medicine Practices in Kadugolla Tribes: A sociological Study of Chitradurga District.

Objectives:

- To study the historical background of the traditional medicine system.
- To study nature of the Kadugolla tribal medicine system by using plant products.
- To identification of Plant species, parts used and treating diseases.

- To study different types of tribal medicine treatments in Kadugolla community.

Methods of the study:

In the present study, the field work has been carried out by using special methods in order to collect information from the tribal's regarding the various practice of traditional medicinal system. Hence I have selected some of the villages as a study area. I gathered both qualitative quantitative data through the observations, questionnaire, interview schedule, and purposive sampling. Secondary data was collected from various University libraries, literature survey and internet data.

Analysis of the data:

In my field work, I have collected qualitative and quantitative information for the analysis of information we are using for the research tools, coding, decoding, tabulation etc.

Table-1: Plants used for medicinally by Nomadic or Semi nomadic tribe of Kadugolla in Chitradurga

Ailments	Scientific/Local Names and Parts Used.	Medicine Preparation	Types of Treatments of Medicine.
Food Poisoning	Hibiscus saddariffa. Khatti pendi. Sepals.	A few sepals are boiled in a glass of water.	The infusion of sepals is given to the patient which leads to vomiting.
Epilepsy	Commelina bengalensis linn. Mothi deni. Roots.	20gm Powder of roots is mixed with the equal amount of jaggary and small sized pills are prepared.	Two pills in a day one in the morning and one in the evening for 6-7 days in case of adults and one pills in a day in case children and women.
Prevention of Pregnancy	A)Daucus carota Linn. Gajar. Seeds. B)Syzygium heyneanun. Lahan jamun. Bark.	70gms seeds are ground to powder. Bark in the west side of the tree is removed and powdered.	5gms seed powder is given to the women twice a day for 14day from the 4 th day of menstruation. Spoonful powder is given to the women as a single dose on the 5 th day of menstruation.
Fistula	Achyranthes aspera Linn Aghanda. Leaves.	The leaves are crushed and a paste prepared	Leaves paste applied externally at night until relief is felt.
Kidney Stone	Ensete superbum cheesm. Jangli keli. Fresh tender.	Fresh tender peduncle is cut and used	About half foot peduncle raw it leads to excessive urination and later relief is felt from kidney stone.
Diabetes	A) Gymnema Sylvestre. Bedki. Fresh leaves. B) Calotropis gigantean. Rui. Fresh flowers.	Fresh leaves are plucked in the early morning. Fresh flowers are plucked in the early morning	One leaf is eaten as such in the morning for 5days. 7flowers are eaten every morning for 21 days.
Skin Diseases	Cassia tora. Powadya. Seeds.	Seeds are finely powdered and mixed in coconut oil to prepare a paste.	This paste is applied on affected part till cured.

Body Pain	Bombax ceiba. Sawari. Leaves.	Few leaves are crushed and soaked in water	The water extract is added to hot water and bath is given to the patient.
Asthma /Polio	Helicteres isora. Hedamuri. Leaves, roots and bark.	Leaves and roots are mixed in a water.	This mixture is taken twice a day till cured.
Stomach Pain	Plumeria rubra L.	5-10 gm. of fresh root made into paste is mixed with ghee	Administered once a day against Stomach pain also cure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The nomadic tribal in the Kadugolla's are living in Chitradurga district in Karnataka. But the data regarding tribal people and medicinal plants are collected from some parts of Chitradurga. The location of study area are Challakere, Holalkere, Hiriur, Hosurga etc. The tribal people were interviewed and the samples of medicines were collected. If the plants were unknown then they were identified by the exports. Most of the medicinal preparations of these tribes matched with those mentioned in Ayurveda and those medicinal preparations. More than one plant is used for same disease. The members of Tribal community were sharing the knowledge regarding traditional method of preparing the herbal medicines, local names of plants, parts used for various diseases etc.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

In this study, 35 medicinal plant species were studied. But some of them were given in the observation table with their method of preparation, mode of treatment, parts of plants used, scientific and local names etc. It is observed that medicinal preparations were practiced scientifically. The knowledge of herbal medicines for preparations, types of treatment to cure the diseases is transmitted one generation to another generation. The contribution of traditional medicine to the modern medicine is worth nothing. Many drugs are made by the scientists with the help of the folk knowledge of traditional medicine. Now a day the scientists are also studying the drugs against Aids, herpes, psoriasis, hypertension, jaundice, asthma, tuberculosis, leprosy, rheumatism etc.

SUGGESTION:

If we encourage the nomads medicinal practices we can cure many more diseases with their indigenous knowledge and method of practices, for this just we need to support and provide a chance to them to come up with their ideas and to implement the practice worldwide. By this we can

educate them about society and make them to understand the life style of modern society.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that the role of herbal medicine and their role in the treatment of different diseases among the tribal peoples are crucial. This helps the agriculturist along with agriculture. This medicinal practices also benefits the rural peoples to get medicine for the various diseases free of cost, who can't able to go for highly technical treatments which costs more. They use many indigenous forest plants, flowers, roots, seeds, fruits, leaves, barks and weeds in their traditional treatment. This will benefit the improvement of traditional and cultural medicinal practices, which upholds the indigenous tradition in Global level. These peoples use plants not only medicinal practices but also in other purposes like constructions of huts, furniture's, Agricultural tools etc. If the traditional knowledge is associated with scientific and modern medicine system, it will be the new revolution in the medicine. By this practice many disease can cured easily with no effort of high technique.

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